

ISic3133

I.Sicily inscription 3133

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Underground cemetery of Predio Maltese

Coordinates

37.076927, 15.286311

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330152

1. Εὐτυχία ἢ πιστὴ ἢ θυγά
2. τηρ Τρυγῆτου ἢ γυνὴ
3. Πρίσκου ἢ ἀπὸ Ὀρτησιαν
4. ὦν ἐνθάδε κῆτε ἐτῶν τ
5. ριακόντα δυῶν

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645474

PHI 330152

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 27.0662

Agnello, S.L. 1975-1976. Interventi di restauro nel cimitero del predio Maltese a Siracusa. *Archivio Storico Siracusano*. n.s. 4: 29-36. At 35-36

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 34 n.156

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